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SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract This deliverable describes the design and development process of the final version of the WIMBY platform containing the interactive map and general forum tools. The iterative design approach from the first part of the project was continued to ensure that the needs of the end users and feedback from testing were taken along in the process. In the second part of the WIMBY project the focus was more on integrating datasets and models from consortium partners. How these datasets and models were developed and visualised is described comprehensively. The results of the last co-creation activity with the consortium partners are explained as well as the integration of the forum and map. The WIMBY platform was presented on several conferences and events and feedback was gathered from interested stakeholders. This feedback was integrated in the development of the final version of the tools. The technical requirements included in the final and publicly available version of the WIMBY map (map.wimby.eu) and forum (forum.wimby.eu) are described in detail.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
AEP	Annual energy output
ENMs	Ecological Niche Models
EZ	Exclusion Zones
GIS	Geographical Information System
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCOE	Levelised Cost of Electricity
LULC	Land Use and Land Cover Change
ML	Machine Learning
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
O&M	Operations & Maintenance
OSM	OpenStreetMap
SF	Shadow Flicker
TSO	Transmission System Operator
WIMBY	Wind In My Backyard
WSI	Wind farm Sensitivity Index

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The WIMBY online platform, containing the interactive map and forum tools, is one of the key developments of the WIMBY project. The interactive map brings together most of the datasets and models that were created in the project and enables the general public to access information that is normally only available for experts. The tool makes it possible to explore spatial datasets concerning impacts, constraints and enabling factors for wind energy planning. Users can even simulate a potential wind farm themselves in an area of interest and learn about the generated energy, regulations that apply and possible positive and negative impacts to consider. These simulations can be saved and shared with other interested stakeholders, for instance by using the other tool in the platform, the WIMBY forum. This complementary tool offers the possibility for stakeholders to discuss a multitude of topics within wind energy planning, access descriptions of the datasets in the map and help guides.

The design approach outlined in the first half of the project (Bakelants et al., 2024) was continued and built further on in the second part. The project team made sure to align the design and development of the map and the forum to ensure a positive user experience for users of both tools. The integration of datasets and models developed in work packages 1, 2 and 4 continued from the first version of the map in an iterative way. Together with project partners the visualisation of the datasets and the forum structure was co-created in the third year of the project.

To ensure external feedback, both the map and forum have also been presented during several events and conferences throughout the project lifetime, and this feedback was integrated in the development.

In summary, the goal of task T5.3 “Web-GIS interactive forum co-creation and assessment (frontend)” was achieved: a final version of the interactive map and forum were conceptualised and developed based on stakeholder needs. In a next step, we will look for opportunities to further improve the platform and extent capabilities that are recognized as useful by users but go beyond the scope of the WIMBY project.

1. INTRODUCTION

Important outcomes of the WIMBY project are the decision-making tools that enable stakeholders to access information, engage with other stakeholders and consider the possibility of a new planned wind farm. The immersive 3D tool enables stakeholders to visualise new wind turbines in a specific landscape in a realistic way. The general forum connects stakeholders and makes it possible to share experiences and discuss specific topics concerning wind farm planning. Finally, the interactive map enables users to access spatial datasets in a straightforward way and simulate the layout, impacts, enablers etc. of a possible new wind farm. In this deliverable we focus on the two tools part of the WIMBY online platform: the WIMBY interactive map and the general forum.

In task T5.3 “Web-GIS interactive forum co-creation and assessment (frontend)”, the goal is to develop a web based interactive map to bring together the results of work packages 1, 2 and 4 of the WIMBY project. The web-based platform combines an interactive map and a forum to enable stakeholders to discuss the results of their simulations and other topics related to wind farm development. This task was linked to two deliverables: D5.1 which was already submitted in month 18 (Bakelants et al., 2024) and this deliverable (D5.2). Here we explain in detail the continuous work on the design and development of the WIMBY platform. This deliverable therefore focuses on the improvements and updates made in the second half of the WIMBY project from month 18-35.

In the METHODOLOGY section of this deliverable, the design approach of the WIMBY tools in the second part of the project is explained, as well as the process of creating and integrating the datasets and models in the interactive map. The final co-creation activity is described together with the technical analysis and development approach. In the RESULTS section, the final versions of the interactive map and forum available at map.wimby.eu and forum.wimby.eu are explained in detail including an overview of the functionalities.

2. METHODOLOGY

As described in Bakelants et al. (2024), the design of the platform was inspired by the design thinking approach. How this methodology was applied in the second half of the project is explained in the first part of the methodology. In the second part, an overview is listed of the datasets and models that were integrated in the final version of the interactive map. For each one, a brief explanation clarifies how they were created. For more technical information about each tool or dataset we refer to their respective deliverables. The third and fourth part of this section explain the co-creation of the platform and the technical approach.

2.1 Design approach

In month 18–35 we built further on the design and analysis work that was done in the first half of the project. In the second half the focus shifted more from creating the framework of the tool to the integration and visualisation of the different datasets. What stayed the same however, is the aim to put the target audience (interested audience, specialised users and education sector) at the centre of the process to make sure the developed tool would meet their needs. We kept iterating through the different phases of the design thinking approach we adopted from the start: first empathising with our users and defining the problem, secondly ideating a solution, thirdly visualising and testing with a prototype and finally implementing the solutions in the WIMBY platform. This is also reflected in the development phase where we created multiple versions of the tools while integrating feedback from testing. In the RESULTS section the final ideation exercise organised in year 3 of the project is explained in detail.

2.2 Datasets and models for the WIMBY Map

Below the methods to develop the different datasets and models that were integrated in the WIMBY map are explained. They range from enablers, constraints and impacts that are important to consider when looking for a good location for a new wind farm. The following datasets and models are discussed:

1. Wind resource & terrain and ruggedness index
2. Birds and bat's collision risk

3. Land and marine animals for pilot sites
4. Landscape scenicness
5. Scenarios of wind power deployment in 2050
6. Exclusion zones
7. Existing wind turbines
8. Wind farm layout and annual energy output
9. Regulations
10. Levelised Cost of Electricity and transmission cost model
11. Noise impact
12. Shadow flicker impact
13. Land use and land cover change impact
14. Human health impacts
15. Job creation
16. Regionalized climate change impacts
17. Local benefits

Most of the models and datasets are available on the scale of the European continent, otherwise it is mentioned in the description.

2.2.1 Wind resource & terrain and ruggedness index

The wind-resource and terrain-related data layers in the WIMBY interactive map are derived from the data of the New European Wind Atlas.

The wind resource layers are produced by consecutive downscaling of wind climatologies from global (ERA5) to mesoscale (WRF) to microscale (WASP) resolutions. The original microscale data were updated to include additional years and improve the microscale downscaling (Hahmann et al. 2024b). In this dataset, the wind climate statistics for each point on a 50 m × 50 m grid comprise the wind speed distribution for 12 sectors and two heights. The distributions are given as parameters of a Weibull distribution for each sector. In the WIMBY interactive map, we display the ten-year mean (2014–2023) of wind speed and power density (energy contained in the wind) at 100 m and 200 m, calculated as the sum of all sectors for each vertical level. These data are used for further modelling in the optimisation and AEP calculation (see section 2.2.8). For other applications (e.g. 2.2.2 bird and bat collision risk and 2.2.5 Scenarios of wind power sections), some WIMBY models require a description of how wind speed changes over time. The full NEWA time series is large, slow to generate and hard to work with. Instead,

we created a 12-month × 24-hour table of average wind speeds using ERA5 data from 2013 to 2022. Due to the known biases in wind speed in ERA5 over complex terrain (NEWA), we recommend bias-correcting the 12 x 24 mean wind speed using the GWA-derived bias correction ratio (defined as GWA2 divided by ERA5) at the turbine site, as proposed in (Dörenkämper et al., 2020).

The terrain elevation provides information on the grid point elevation above the sea level, and the ruggedness index (Shawn J. Riley et al., 1999) quantifies terrain complexity on a scale from 0 (flat) to 1 (highly rugged), based on elevation variability. Low values indicate sites suitable for wind turbine installation, while high values denote challenging terrain that may increase construction complexity and affect wind flow. This index is thus a key parameter in wind energy site assessment and planning.

2.2.2 Birds and bat's collision risk

Since flying animals can fatally collide with wind-farm infrastructure, we included layers of risk to European birds and bats from fatal collisions. To generate layers reflecting mortality and risk, we used a dataset of recorded collisions for birds and bats from published papers and reports, compiled and made available by Thaxter et al. (2017). We used two different approaches for bats and birds.

For birds, our approach focused on estimating the reported comparative risk posed by collisions to 108 species and is described in Etard et al. (2025). Our custom framework built upon risk/vulnerability approaches developed for conservation biology (Foden et al., 2019). We considered that risk emerged from the overlap of (1) reported impacts (total estimated number of fatalities at the species-level, which accounted for current exposure to wind turbines; termed 'impact index') and (2) intrinsic vulnerability to these impacts (i.e., the degree to which species may be affected by collision mortality). We estimated these two dimensions of risk (impacts and vulnerability) separately, independently deriving the 'impact index' and the 'vulnerability index' at the species level. To estimate the impact index, we employed a quantitative synthesis, quantifying collision-mortality rates at the species-level from fatality-count data compiled in (Thaxter et al., 2017). By combining the estimated rates with spatial information on species suitable areas and current wind-turbine deployment, we derived (1). Further, we obtained an estimate of species' vulnerability (2) from their ecological characteristics (considering generation length, clutch size, and estimates of

European suitable area). Such characteristics were assumed to reflect the degree to which species may be able to cope with disturbances. Finally, we overlapped the estimated relative vulnerability with the estimated impacts. We classified species into four risk categories depending on their relative position in the risk space: for instance, we considered species to be at high relative risk when relatively more vulnerable and more impacted; at high latent risk when exhibiting higher relative vulnerability but lower relative impacts. We then mapped the number of species (i.e., pseudo species richness) in each category, by stacking species suitability maps obtained following Jung (2023) for the species in each risk category. We thereby assessed where species falling into the risk categories might occur in Europe. The layer displayed on the WIMBY interactive map shows the number of bird species assessed to be at higher relative risk or high latent risk in each grid cell (27 species fell in these categories of the 108 species assessed). More details on the obtention of the layers can be found in Etard et al. (2025).

For bats, we assessed collision-mortality rates at the species level, that is, the number of collision fatalities per wind turbine and per year, using data from Thaxter et al. (2017). Through a quantitative synthesis, using a statistical model where the number of recorded fatalities was fitted as a response, and different predictors were used to explain variation in the number of recorded fatalities across species (Etard et al., 2024). From the model, we estimated average collision-mortality rates across 22 European species. Using spatial data on species' areas of suitability in Europe, obtained following Jung (2023), we summarised estimated collision-mortality rates at the assemblage level, providing summary statistics of collision-mortality rates across all species occurring in a grid cell (of 22 species). The layer on the interactive map shows the number of fatalities estimated in each grid cell across all species that occur in the given location (total average number of fatalities across all species, per turbine per year: cumulative impact).

2.2.3 Land and marine animals for pilot sites

Datasets are available for three pilot sites of the WIMBY project: Styria (Austria), the island of Pantelleria (Italy) and Rogaland (Norway).

Land habitat suitability maps for Styria

While the most obvious effect of wind farms is mortality of animals due to collision with rotor blades or turbine towers, construction of wind farms and

related infrastructure also results in habitat modification (Diffendorfer et al., 2019). Thus, layers were produced to visualize areas of high suitability for a set of selected animal species. The selection of species is based on four criteria – habitat (forest and woodland-dwelling), migration (non-migratory), conservation status (threatened) and data availability (at least 100 presence points). The maps were created using advanced statistical tools (Kuhn, 2008) and have a high level of detail, with each map covering areas with pixel cells as small as 250 meters by 250 meters. These tools analysed various factors that influence where species are likely to live, for example land cover, topography and climate variables. Details on the modelling procedures can be found in deliverable D1.8 (Diengdoh et al., 2025). The accuracy of the habitat suitability maps was assessed using the Area Under the Curve (AUC) of the Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve (Fielding & Bell, 1997) and the True Skilled Statistic (Allouche et al., 2006).

The maps assign a habitat suitability value to each pixel cell, ranging from 0.0 to 1.0. A value of 0.0 means the area is completely unsuitable for a species, while 1.0 means it is highly suitable. To make the data easier to use in the WIMBY interactive map, these values were simplified into two categories, for each species separately: 0, indicating areas that are unsuitable, and 1, indicating suitable habitat for the specific species, respectively. It is important to note that just because an area is marked as "suitable" must not mean the species is actually living there. The maps only indicate that the area has the right conditions for the species to survive, such as the right climate, vegetation, or other environmental factors. Whether the species is actually present depends also on other factors, like movement patterns or human activity.

To provide a broader perspective, we also created "summed habitat suitability maps" for the respective species groups. These maps combine the binary habitat maps of the species within each group (amphibians, birds, butterflies) into a single layer (Diengdoh et al., 2025). The resulting maps display values ranging from 0 to 9 for amphibians, 0 to 6 for birds and 0 to 4 for butterflies. A value of 0 indicates that the area is not suitable for any species within the respective group, while the maximum value (e.g. 4 for butterflies) indicates that the area is suitable for all species in that group. As only one bat species was analysed, no summed habitat suitability map was prepared for the bats.

Marine habitat suitability maps for Pantelleria

Ecological Niche Models (ENMs) are computational tools used in ecology and conservation biology to predict species distribution by considering environmental factors. The maps obtained through ENMs assign a habitat suitability value ranging from 0.0 to 1.0. A value of 0.0 means the area is unsuitable for a species, while 1.0 means it is highly suitable. In the context of offshore wind farm siting, they can help to select sites where impacts on marine species are minimised. We used ENMs to obtain habitat suitability maps for some target species, for which occurrence data were available for the area of Pantelleria Island. Target species considered were selected from the list of Descriptor 1 (Marine Biodiversity) of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive ('Council Directive 92/43/EEC', 1992). In particular, habitat suitability maps were created for six coastal bony fish (*Coris julis*, *Diplodus sargus*, *D. vulgaris*, *Epinephelus marginatus*, *Sarpa salpa* and *Spicara maena*), one shark (*Mustelus punctulatus*), three rays (*Leucoraja melitensis*, *Raja clavata* and *Torpedo marmorata*), the loggerhead turtle (*Caretta caretta*) and two dolphins (*Stenella coeruleoalba* and *Tursiops truncatus*). Environmental factors considered were concentration of nitrates (Data-Interpolating Variational Analysis DIVA interpolation, $\mu\text{mol/l}$), chlorophyll-a (mean at mean depth, mg/m^3), phosphates (DIVA interpolation, $\mu\text{mol/l}$), silicates (DIVA interpolation, $\mu\text{mol/L}$), dissolved oxygen (DIVA interpolation, ml/l), pH (DIVA interpolation), bathymetry (meters), sea surface salinity (annual mean, Practical Salinity Scale-PSS) and sea surface temperature (annual mean, $^{\circ}\text{C}$). Final habitat suitability maps had a resolution of ~ 9.2 km and were obtained using an ensemble prediction of four statistical models: Generalized Linear Model, Random Forest, MaxEnt, and Support Vector Machine. For more information we refer to deliverable D1.8 (Diengdoh et al., 2025).

Seabird Wind farm Sensitivity Index for Rogaland

Seabirds are primarily vulnerable to offshore wind power plants through collision-risks and habitat disruption (Dierschke et al., 2016; Drewitt & Langstan, 2006). Many seabirds' flight height is similar to the rotor height of wind turbines, making them vulnerable for collisions and mortality. Many seabirds further show avoidance behaviour to offshore wind turbines, leading to habitat disruptions, higher energy use and barrier-effects (Fauchald et al., 2023).

To assess the impact of offshore wind power on seabirds, Garthe & Hüppop, (2004) developed a wind farm sensitivity index based on nine vulnerability

factors comprising flight behaviour (flight manoeuvrability, flight attitude, percent of time flying and nocturnal flight activity), general behaviour (disturbance by ship and helicopter traffic as well as flexibility in habitat use) and status (biogeographical population size, adult survival rate and European threat and conservation status). The seabird wind farm sensitivity layer for the Norwegian pilot site in Rogaland builds on this index.

Observational data on species from a number of different datasets (see Fauchald et al., 2023 for details) is combined with environmental data on habitat suitability using species distribution modelling to generate the wind farm sensitivity index (more information in Diengdoh et al., 2025).

2.2.4 Landscape scenicness

Scenicness refers to the widely shared perception of the visual appeal of landscape features such as topography, vegetation, water bodies, and other natural elements. To the best of the author's knowledge, only two publicly available databases with a 1 km × 1 km spatial resolution currently quantify landscape scenicness in Europe: the crowd-sourced, survey-based ScenicOrNot database for Great Britain (*ScenicOrNot*, 2015), and an empirically modelled scenicness map for Germany (Roth et al., 2018).

To address the lack of landscape scenicness data at the European scale, a machine learning (ML) model was trained using the ScenicOrNot dataset (R. Chen et al., 2024). The dataset was divided into training (80%) and test (20%) subsets. To prevent geographically biased estimates, we also applied spatially stratified sampling. Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB) classifier was selected as the primary algorithm for predicting landscape scenicness. Hyperparameter tuning was performed using randomized search over 10 iterations, optimizing model performance through 5-fold cross-validation. Model training incorporated a range of contextual features derived from publicly available, high-resolution spatial datasets (a detailed description of these variables and their calculation methods is provided in deliverable D2.5 (R. Chen et al., 2023). Among those, CORINE Land Cover (CLC) categories, naturalness, global horizontal irradiance, and proximity to inland water bodies emerged as the most influential predictors of landscape scenicness.

The German dataset served as an independent test set to evaluate the model's performance and generalizability. The model demonstrated strong generalizability across different countries, achieving over 80% consistency with survey ratings. The resulting model, which classifies areas in Europe as

either “highly scenic” or “other”, was then applied to predict landscape scenicness across the EU25+4 countries at a 1 km × 1 km spatial resolution (R. Chen et al., 2025).

2.2.5 Scenarios of wind power deployment in 2050

As wind energy costs have decreased dramatically, a future decarbonised European electricity system will feature high shares of wind energy. However, wind turbines can have social and environmental impacts on the local areas where they are sited (McKenna et al., 2025). To address how these social and environmental factors can shape the future deployment of wind and solar in Europe in 2050, we used the power system model, highRES-Europe (Price & Zeyringer, 2022), at the NUTS2 level resolution. This is an electricity system model specifically designed to capture spatial and temporal details of wind power and other renewables in Europe. It simultaneously makes planning decisions (location and installed capacity) and operational decisions for electricity generation, storage, and transmission in a given year, ensuring that supply meets electricity demand at the lowest possible cost while meeting net-zero decarbonisation objectives. The version of highRES-Europe used in this project models 25 EU countries (excluding Cyprus and Malta), as well as Norway, Switzerland, and the UK. Moreover, highRES-Europe was coupled to the JRC-EU-TIMES whole system model (European Commission Joint Research Centre, 2020), providing electricity system boundary conditions, including electricity demand and emissions limits in 2050.

The onshore and offshore wind installed capacities displayed in this layer are estimated considering technical exclusion zones closely aligned with the hard constraints described in the present deliverable, as well as the combination of three levels (low, medium, and high) of prioritisation for social (e.g., setback distances from settlements based on country regulations and landscape scenicness map) and environmental (e.g., protected areas and birds and bats collision risk) factors that can shape wind power deployment in Europe in 2050. The considered levels for the social and environmental factors are: low, representing a permissive scenario, where only the bare minimum land is excluded from wind farm development (a future where society does not prioritise the dimension); medium, capturing a more middle-ground future based on central values for the range of each restriction; and high, considering a very restrictive case, where the dimension is prioritised at a local level and onshore wind

energy is mainly diminished in a European context. A detailed explanation about the dimensions and assumptions for this layer can be found in deliverable D4.5 (Price et al., 2025).

2.2.6 Exclusion zones

Within the WIMBY project, Exclusion Zones (EZ) refer to spatial areas that restrict the deployment of wind turbines across Europe. These zones are classified into hard constraints, which are legally or physically prohibited for turbine installation (e.g., national parks, buildings, steep terrain), and soft constraints, which represent buffer zones around hard constraints where development is limited but not strictly prohibited. This development covers the processing, standardisation, and integration of exclusion zones into the TOPFARM wind farm optimisation tool. Data on hard and soft constraints for all WIMBY countries is shown in Table 3: Exclusion zones and their hard and soft constraints as buffers in meters. The processing of every subcategory Table 3 in the ANNEX, and the processing method is detailed in deliverable D2.2 (Hahmann et al., 2024a).

To ensure compatibility with the TOPFARM optimisation tool, all exclusion zone layers were converted to a polygon vector format. Raster data was vectorised, and point or line vector data were buffered by 1 m to form polygons or multipolygons. All layers were reprojected to the ETRS89-extended / LAEA Europe coordinate system (EPSG: 3035), which is consistent with the projection used for NEWA microscale data.

2.2.7 Existing wind turbines

A harmonised database of wind turbine locations and technical specifications was developed by integrating national datasets (Bundesnetzagentur: Marktstammdatenregister (MaStR), Germany; Energistyrelsen: Stamdataregisteret for Vindkraftanlæg, Denmark; Energimyndigheten: Vindbrukskollen – Energimyndigheten, Sweden) European-wide sources, OpenStreetMap (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2025), Wind Power (*The Wind Power. Europe Wind Farms Database*, 2005) and EMODnet (Martín Míguez et al., 2019). This is explained in deliverable D1.2 (Hahmann et al., 2024b). Missing attributes were imputed using random forest models, and a custom algorithm was implemented to associate wind farm-level data with individual turbines. The final dataset includes turbine coordinates, type, hub height, rotor diameter, rated power, cut-in and cut-out wind speeds, power and thrust curves, as well as commissioning and

decommissioning dates. It has been extended to cover all of Europe and is hosted in YODA. While open-source parameters are publicly accessible, licensed data are restricted to consortium partners. WindPower data, the main contributor, approved the display of turbine positions on the WIMBY interactive map, although external sharing remains prohibited.

2.2.8 Wind farm layout and annual energy output

We optimise wind turbine layout in the WIMBY map using the EZ layers (section 2.2.6) and microscale wind resource data with the open-source tool TOPFARM (TOPFARM, 2018). The resulting layout maximises the Annual Energy Production (AEP) for a set number of turbines and positions, considering constraints like minimum spacing and boundary restrictions. The microscale data, with exclusion zones from EZ layers including protected areas and roads, characterise the terrain's non-uniform wind resources. Wind resource data accounts for elevation and land use changes, such as hills being windier than valleys and winds decreasing around forests. However, wake calculation and layout optimisation do not consider terrain variations.

The annual energy output (AEP) is calculated as the sum of the power produced by each wind turbine, using the local distribution of wind speed and a wind turbine's power curve. The local wind speed distribution per sector is taken from the turbine location at the free stream direction. To account for wake losses, we used the NOJ Jensen wake deficit model with a squared sum superposition model implemented in the PyWake tool (PyWake, 2018). The wind farm capacity factor is estimated by the AEP divided by the potential energy produced by the wind farm when operational 100% of the time.

2.2.9 Regulations

Setback distances are a key element in wind energy planning, ensuring safety, well-being, and ecological protection; yet overly stringent or primarily politically driven requirements can significantly slow down development or bring it to a halt. The map contains data for national and regional laws and regulations or official guidelines governing setback distances of wind turbines to different types of infrastructure onshore (airports, residential buildings and residential areas, gas pipelines, military areas, nature conservation areas, transmission lines, radars, railway lines, highways and primary roads, flowing waters and standing waters) and

offshore (gas pipelines, offshore cables, offshore platforms shipping lanes) down to a NUTS-2 level. The data was identified through a systematic web search based on predefined keywords and complemented by written or oral exchanges (online meetings) with 18 (cross-)national wind energy experts working in administration, development or consultancy (Bucha, 2025). Keywords were divided into primary, secondary and tertiary tiers. Searches were conducted using at least one term from each tier in combination. Primary terms consisted of the name of the respective country (for example, Austria) and, where wind energy-related legislation or guidelines were typically issued regionally, the relevant region (for example, Burgenland). Secondary terms included ('onshore wind turbines' OR 'offshore wind turbines') AND ('setback distance' OR 'minimum distance'), while tertiary terms comprised the various kinds of infrastructures analysed (e.g. residential areas, airports). Keywords were refined iteratively during the screening process to improve the precision of search results. To increase the number of search results, keywords were translated into at least one of the main languages spoken in the country or region, using AI-based translation. For an EU-wide comparison of the national and regional setback distances, formulas have been assimilated (e.g. all distances were unified into meters) and the median calculated based on four turbine types (the ones provided in the WIMBY map), resulting in a range of minimum and distances for each category. More information can be found in deliverable D2.10 (Bucha et al. (2024).

2.2.10 Levelised Cost of Electricity and transmission cost model

Two separate models are used and then added together to estimate the Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE) of the wind farm. The first is the Open-Source Region-specific LCOE (ORC) model, which calculates a wind farm's Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE) by synthesising project costs and energy production. It individually models and sums the costs for Capital Expenditures (CapEx), Operational Expenditures (OpEx), and Decommissioning. The model adjusts key cost drivers—including Balance-of-System, land lease, and O&M—as well as the financial discount rate, based on country-specific data, to achieve regional specificity.

A grid connection model has been developed in WIMBY to suggest preliminary routes of grid connection for potential wind farms in Europe and estimate the associated costs. The cost estimation is based on the distance from the centroid of the considered wind farm to the nearest substation in

the country. The method used in this model consists mainly of the following three steps:

(1) Retrieving nearest substation: In this step the nearest substation in the same country as the wind farm located is found, which has the shortest geodesic distance to the wind farm centroid.

(2) Preliminary route planning: In this step the preliminary route from the wind farm centroid to the substation found in step one is planned. The algorithm developed in this model starts by first placing the transmission towers along a straight line (not accounting the elevation variations) between the wind farm and the substation, with a relatively equal spacing between them that is subject to a default maximal threshold (500 m). Then the arrangement of the towers is adjusted to avoid the transmission line contacting the ground due to elevation changes. Finally, if part of the transmission route violates the considered exclusion zones, the route segment that enters the exclusive zone will be replaced by an arc with the segment length as the diameter, and the transmission towers on this arc will be placed accordingly. After the locations of the transmission towers are fixed, the total length of the transmission line can then be computed by taking the elevation differences between neighbouring towers into consideration.

(3) Connection cost estimation: To estimate the total cost of grid connection, country-specific exploratory unit costs (per km) of single and double-circuit AC transmission lines are first derived for Europe. These numbers are derived based on openly available cost estimation data from an American Transmission System Operator (TSO) (Transmission Cost Estimation Guide, 2025) for the transmission lines, and labour costs data from the International Labour Organisation (ILO) (*Consumer Price Index (2010=100)*, n.d.) to adjust the country-specific costs caused by labour cost differences. Using exploratory unit cost for the specific country, the total grid connection cost can then be computed for the preliminary route found in step two. To account for the different costs of installing transmission towers and lines in different terrain slopes, the cost computation is done by segments, with the line segments connecting to a tower on a steeper slope seeing higher thus penalized costs (if the slope is less than 5°, no penalty is applied).

This model has been developed primarily to provide a rough yet relevant estimate of connecting a potential wind farm in Europe to the grid, based on publicly available data. It is also designed to provide results quickly,

enabling interactive usage. Thus, the route planning algorithm is designed to give preliminary routing suggestions instead of detailed routing planning, as the latter would require solving the time-consuming routing search/optimisation problems for transmission lines. This model is developed in Python and utilises several open source geodata libraries. The overall runtime of the model itself is computationally light, but the entire procedure takes 5 to 15 seconds, primarily due to the complex geometries in the exclusion zone layer. A detailed explanation is provided in deliverable D2.2 (Hahmann et al., 2024a).

2.2.11 Noise impact

We estimate the A-weighted sound power level at various wind speeds of each turbine using a multi-output, histogram-based gradient boosting model that was trained on a large measurement dataset (about 1,470 turbines, 3–12 m/s) provided via the EMD Nord2000 framework (EMD-International, 2025). Sound propagation and attenuation from each turbine to each receiver follow ISO 9613-2:2024 (International Organization for Standardization, 2024). At each receiver, the predicted sound level equals the turbine's sound power level, plus any directivity adjustment (if applied), minus the total attenuation accumulated along the path. The model distinguishes turbine generated noise from existing ambient sources (e.g., highways, railways, airports, industry) by integrating European Environmental Agency noise layers (European Environment Agency, n.d.), and models ground and barrier attenuation alongside geometric divergence and atmospheric absorption.

Inputs for the calculation include rated power, hub height, rotor diameter, the European Environmental Agency noise maps (European Environment Agency, n.d.), Copernicus DEM map, provided by the European Space Agency (ESA), with either a 30 meters or 90 meters resolution (European Union, 2022); and hourly wind speed data from the bias-corrected ERA5 database (Hersbach et al., 2020). The model is explained in detail in deliverable D2.3 (Sacchi et al., 2023).

2.2.12 Shadow flicker impact

Shadow flicker (SF) is the intermittent shading produced by rotating wind-turbine blades and can be a notable nuisance for nearby residents. The SF values on the WIMBY interactive map are estimated as exposure time at the locations, using our physical model, the WIMBY_SF tool (H. Chen, 2025) that

calculates the sun's relative position throughout the year, and projects turbine shadows across 20m x 20m Digital Surface Models (resampled from Copernicus DEM map (European Union, 2022) that capture terrain and obstructing features, and applies turbine parameters (turbine height and rotor diameter) with the chosen temporal resolution. The temporal resolution we applied for the WIMBY interactive map is at 4-minute intervals for every 14 days over the year, which provides a good balance between accuracy and computational effort (H. Chen et al., 2025; Sacchi et al., 2025).

2.2.13 Land use and land cover change impact

Sentinel-2 tiles (Drusch et al., 2012) were downloaded from Google Earth Engine (Google Sentinel-2 Cloud, 2023) with <5% cloud coverage for 2015 and 2023. Change detection maps were generated using the Orfeo toolbox (Grizonnet et al., 2017) comparing true-color images between time periods. Raster values were extracted for each wind turbine location plus four neighbouring pixels, with negative values indicating new construction and positive values indicating removal.

The statistical analysis employed DBSCAN (Schubert et al., 2017) clustering (minimum 2 turbines, maximum 1500m distance) to define a wind farm. Convex and concave hulls are generated to represent farm boundaries. The change pixels within the wind farms are intersected with EEA's CORINE land cover data (European Environment Agency, 2019) and change values are calculated as absolute area and percentage change per land-use category within these boundaries to quantify land use impacts from wind energy development. The approach is explained in detail in deliverable D1.4 (Mikovits, 2024).

2.2.14 Human health impacts

To conduct analysis on accidents, a comprehensive database of wind farm accidents was compiled using various sources such as open access reports from industry, authorities and independent private organisations. The collected information was then verified and validated to ensure high levels of completeness, consistency, and accuracy. This was achieved using a combination of web scraping, natural language processing (NLP), and machine learning techniques, including artificial intelligence-based approaches. Accident records were then matched with wind park locations from the Windpower Net Database (*The Wind Power. Europe Wind Farms Database*, 2005), using detailed information on turbine types and

geographic coordinates. Incidents occurring prior to the year 2000 were excluded due to their limited relevance in terms of frequency and severity. The final dataset comprises 1,243 accidents recorded between 2000 and 2023. Each accident was geographically assigned to its corresponding NUTS2 region, allowing for regional aggregation of accident risks. Fatality rates were normalised per unit of electricity generation (GWe-year), enabling meaningful comparisons across regions and supporting the creation of spatial risk maps. To assess the broader health impacts, accident consequences (i.e., fatalities and injuries) were translated into Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs), a metric that captures health losses due to disabilities, injuries and risk factors. These DALY values were also aggregated at the NUTS2 level, following the same methodology used for fatality rates. Afterwards they were transformed into categories from low to very high. Details of this approach can be found in deliverable D2.3 (Sacchi et al., 2023).

2.2.15 Job creation

A model to estimate job creation for individual farms was created based on a systematic literature review for data acquisition and expert interviews for validation. We searched in the SCOPUS database for combinations of three sets of keywords. The first set included “jobs”, “job creation”, “employment”, “employment creation”, and “employment factor”. The second set was “wind energy”, “wind power”, and “wind turbines”, while the third set presented a locational component by specifically searching for publications related to “Europe”, “EU” and the rest of the world “*”. In total we assessed 162 unique sources from which 70 contained data on job creation for different life cycle stages of wind farms (development, construction, manufacturing, operation and maintenance, and decommissioning) and job types (direct, indirect, and induced). We transformed all the gathered data to a common indicator, an employment factor defined as job-years per installed capacity (job-years/MW). We run linear regressions and descriptive statistics on the data to find commonalities that would allow us to make estimations of job creation for individual farms (details provided in Bucha et al., 2023). Two models were derived out of it and the one that provides most functionality (can take into consideration turbine capacity, number of turbines, country of deployment, and whether the installation is onshore or offshore) was transformed into a public open source python package (del Villar et al., 2025). We validated the job creation estimations through five expert

interviews with consultants and managers responsible for planning, operating and decommissioning wind farms as well as with a representative of a European wind energy lobby institution. A further validation (Klap & Ramirez Camargo, 2023) was conducted by scaling up the calculation for the entire European wind farm fleet and comparing the results to estimations made by WindEurope (WindEurope, 2023; Klap & Ramirez Camargo, 2023).

2.2.16 Regionalized climate change impacts

Climate change impacts were obtained from a particularly developed life cycle assessment (LCA) model that can be applied to both on- and offshore wind turbines. As a starting point, an existing LCA model was adjusted to capture potential climate change impacts all over Europe (Sacchi et al., 2019). A cradle-to-grave approach was adopted considering raw material extraction, component manufacturing and transportation, installation, maintenance and end-of-life treatment. Particular emphasis was given to capture regional conditions in the life cycle inventory (LCI) collection. To obtain regionalized LCI data, the location of the turbines was used to collect a set of information. That information is the sea depth, used for sizing the foundations and obtaining the material requirements of offshore turbines, the distance to the next electric connection point with the electricity grid and the transportation distance from component manufacturing up to the final installation. Apart from monopile foundations, LCI data of two floating foundations, a semi-submersible floating foundation (30–60 meters depths) and a spar buoy floating foundation (deeper than 60 meters depths) were adopted from (Garcia-Teruel et al., 2022). For the electric connection of the turbine, the distance to the next grid connection point was obtained based on a publicly available dataset representing the European electricity grid network (Xiong et al., 2024). Two main turbine manufacturing locations were chosen to approximate the distance between manufacturing facility and final installation. The model first calculated and then chose the minimum distance of the two locations.

As a functional unit, kilowatt hours generated electricity and delivered to the electricity grid was selected and consequently, results are expressed in gCO₂eq/kWh. Therefore, the annual electricity yield as determined by the DTU model (see section 2.2.8) was assumed over a lifetime of 20 years. Obtained climate change impacts were calculated based on the climate change category of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC

et al., 2013). Datasets were obtained from an open-access database published by the Federal Office of the Environment of Switzerland. The development of the LCA model is described more in detail in deliverable D2.8 (Huber & Lavigne Philippot, 2024).

2.2.17 Local benefits

A common misconception is that wind parks solely impose local burdens. In reality, beyond their crucial role in reducing CO₂ emissions, they create employment, contribute to public revenues (e.g., via local taxes and financial participation schemes), and foster broader economic development. The map contains data for national and regional laws, regulations or official guidelines governing financial participation schemes in the sector for onshore wind energy down to a NUTS-2 level (only in the case of Wallonia (Belgium), the scope extends down to the municipal level). The data was identified through a systematic web search based on predefined keywords and complemented by written or oral exchanges (online meetings) with 18 (cross-)national wind energy experts working in administration, development or consultancy. Keywords were divided into primary, secondary and tertiary tiers. Searches were conducted using at least one term from each tier in combination. Primary terms consisted of the name of the respective country (for example, Austria) and, where wind energy-related legislation or guidelines were typically issued regionally, the relevant region (for example, Burgenland). Secondary terms included 'windfall' and 'wind energy', while tertiary terms comprised 'levy', 'tax', 'financial', 'participation', 'compensation' and 'payment'. Keywords were refined iteratively during the screening process to improve the precision of search results. To increase the number of search results, keywords were translated into at least one of the main languages spoken in the country or region, using AI-based neural machine translation. For better comparability, the financial participation schemes were clustered into four groups which were defined along the review of existing schemes: fixed payments (e.g. offering monetary compensation payments or in-kind benefits), debt-based participation (e.g. offering investment opportunities with fixed interest rates), revenue-based participation (e.g. offering compensation payments that are bound to the project's profits) and equity-based participation (e.g. issuing project shares with or without voting rights). More information about this approach can be found in deliverable D2.10 (Bucha et al., 2024).

2.3 Co-creating the WIMBY platform

2.3.1 Data visualization workshop for interactive map

A final co-creation activity with the consortium partners was organised in the second half of the project for the interactive map. The goal was to translate complex and technical datasets to accessible information that could be easily understood by our target audience (interested audience, researchers and education group). To achieve this, a data visualisation workshop was organised with all consortium partners during the General Assembly in Lisbon, Portugal in January 2025.

During this workshop the partners were divided into groups to ideate and prototype the visualisation of a certain dataset. They received drawing material and a print of the WIMBY map layout as a starting point. For each dataset it was analysed whether it would be best integrated as a layer on the map or as a result of the wind farm simulation (side panel). At the end of the workshop the different ideas were discussed with the whole group and sticky notes with remarks were added. The results of this physical workshop are digitally documented with pictures and sticky notes in the WIMBY Miro board.

Below, in Figure 1, the example of the dataset “Levelised Cost of Electricity” is shown with the idea of showing the cable on the map to link the simulated wind farm with the nearest substation.

Figure 1: Example results of data visualization workshop for the dataset Levelised Cost of Electricity.

Afterwards the technical feasibility of the suggestions was examined in detail and priorities were assigned to be used in the development phase. In WP5 monthly meetings the development plan was always discussed with the attending partners.

2.3.1 Co-creating the General Forum

In parallel with the WIMBY Map, the Forum was deployed on the existing VPS server owned by VUB. In the final year of the project co-creation activities focused on aligning its structure with the Map features and on creating thread categories for discussions.

In most cases feedback was collected during open discussions with external stakeholders or through dedicated sessions, both internally with partners and publicly (see Table 1). A “guided navigation” exercise lasting 30 minutes was organised during the final joint policy event in Brussels: the objective was that of collecting as much feedback as possible during a speed session with an expert audience (Figure 2). Each participant could choose one specific action to run on screen, and all other participants could see what happened and comment. The navigation went from the map features to the Forum. Thanks to the feedback received the Forum achieved its final shape and will still undergo final review and edits. Finally Deep Blue and Nazka Mapps created a common Terms and conditions document and updated

the Privacy Policy integrating it with Cognito and Discourse third party services.

Table 1: Overview of co-creation workshops for the conceptualisation of the WIMBY general forum.

Date	Name of event	Target audience	Participants
Between January and September 2025	Internal workshops	partners	15+
October 2024	2 nd AB meeting	Expert advisory board members	6
15/10/2025	Final policy event	Policy makers and researchers	15+

Figure 2: Rebecca Hueting introducing the Map and Forum session during the Final Event in Brussels, 15 October 2025.

A final internal session with Consortium members took place during the last Executive Board meeting in November 2025, to run a final test, decide over categories naming and agree on the contents of the Welcome Kit, where Map and Forum tutorials and detailed description of datasets will be provided (see Figure 3 below).

Forum

- Home
- My posts
- FAQ
- More
- Categories
 - Welcome Kit
 - All categories
- Tags
 - biodiversity
 - eia-procedures

categories tags Latest New Hot Top

New Topic

Welcome Kit
Welcome onboard the WIMBY platform general forum for discussion. Register and start...

- Map - Datasets descriptio...
- Forum - Instructions and tr...
- MAP - Instructions and trai...

General
Create topics here that don't fit into any other existing category.

Public simulations
Share here the link to your simulation. To start a simulation sign-up and start using the WIMBY...

Site Feedback
Discussion about this site, its organization, how it works, and how we can improve it.

- Map - Feedback area
- Forum - Feedback area

Figure 3: WIMBY general forum with discussion categories like the Welcome Kit.

During the different pilot sites workshops the current version of the WIMBY platform was always presented, and feedback was gathered from participants (Figure 4).

The structure of the WIMBY Forum was defined in coherence with the Interactive Map, so as to facilitate user navigation across the different topics. More information about the development of the forum can be found in deliverable D6.2 (Hueting & Cecconi, 2024).

Figure 4: Activity during the pilot site workshops demonstrating the WIMBY platform.

2.4 Data & technical analysis interactive map

2.4.1 Development approach

From the first 18 months of the project, there was already an overview of the datasets to be integrated and functionalities to be added to the WIMBY map as described in deliverable D5.1 (Bakelants et al., 2024).

The development of the WIMBY map was organised using an agile approach. The application evolved thanks to iterative development into the final beta version. The integration of the datasets and models was facilitated by DTU in the same way as explained in deliverable D5.1. Here also an iterative approach was used where more endpoints and layers were added throughout the project period. DTU was responsible for managing the backend, making available data layers in the form of tiles (for example the birds and bats collision risk from section 2.2.2) and vectortiles (for example the exclusion zones from section 2.2.6) and adding endpoints to the WIMBY API (this is explained in Hahmann et al., 2024b).

Below, Figure 5 shows the requirements that were developed in version 1 (indicated with 1), intermediate versions (indicated with 2) and ultimately in the final beta version of the WIMBY map (indicated with 3). Not all requirements envisioned at the design phase of the application were developed, and prioritisation was used to focus on the must haves. This agile approach was also employed when already making a first version of certain datasets and models available in the map which were updated later on in the project and in the map. The beta version of the WIMBY map and platform was presented and launched during the WIMBY final event October 15 in Brussels.

coggle
made for free at coggle.it

Figure 5: Requirements envisioned for the WIMBY map in the design phase of the project. Finalized requirements are indicated with (1) for version 1, (2) for intermediate versions and (3) for the final version.

2.4.2 Implementation of authentication

We introduced a user account in the WIMBY map to make it possible to save a simulation. Authentication was implemented by using AWS Cognito services. This ensures a safe and standardized approach that works well with the tech stack of the WIMBY map, for cloud services AWS servers in Ireland are used. Only a small amount of personal information is stored, this is limited to an email address, username and password.

Using Oauth, the authentication of the WIMBY map is integrated with that of the WIMBY forum. Users who make an account in the WIMBY map or via a link

in the WIMBY forum, will be able to use the same Cognito login to get access to both applications. In the terms of use more information about this is available for the users.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Final version of the WIMBY platform

3.1.1 WIMBY interactive map

Below in Table 2 the list of requirements is shown for the final version of the WIMBY interactive map. Underneath the requirements are explained in detail with screenshots. In this deliverable we focus the explanation on the new or updated requirements in comparison to deliverable D5.1.

The beta version of the WIMBY map is publicly available at <https://map.wimby.eu/>. The application can be roughly divided into two modes: exploration and planning mode. In the exploration mode users can explore datasets at the continental level on the map. In the planning mode, users can draw a polygon on the map to simulate a wind farm and get an overview of the things to take into account like positive and negative impacts, energy output and regulations.

Table 2: Requirements included in the interactive map with the relevant deliverable.

Requirement group	Specific requirement	Relevant deliverable
Help	Welcome popup	D5.1
	Info text layers and wind farm simulation results	D5.1
	Link to dataset description page	D5.2
Wind farm simulation	Draw polygon	D5.1
	Input parameters	D5.2
	Turbine info	D5.1
	My simulation info	D5.2
	Energy output results	D5.1
	Regulation warning	D5.2
	Noise impact on the map	D5.2
	Shadow flicker on the map	D5.2
	Human health impacts	D5.2
Creation of jobs	D5.2	

	Scenicness	D5.2
	Levelised Cost of Electricity	D5.2
	Climate change impact	D5.2
	Land use change	D5.2
	Collision risk	D5.2
	Save simulation	D5.2
Pilot regions	Pilot sites overview layer	D5.1
	Impacts on marine and land fauna layers	D5.2
	Basic information pilot sites	D5.1
About	Terms of Use	D5.2
	Help guide (in the forum)	D5.2
	Contact (in the forum)	D5.2
Map tools	Scale & lat/lon coordinates	D5.1
	Zooming & panning	D5.1
	Search address & region	D5.1
	Change basemap	D5.1
	Zoom to my location	D5.1
	Interactive legend	D5.1
Languages	English, German, Portuguese, Norwegian (Nynorsk and Bokmål) and Italian	D5.2
Existing wind turbines	Existing wind turbines layer	D5.2
Forum functionalities	Link with General forum	D5.2
	Shared authentication	D5.2
Map layers	Wind resource with height selector	D5.1
	Collision risk	D5.2
	Scenicness	D5.2
	Accidents	D5.2
	Noise impact	D5.2
	Hard constraints	D5.2
	Soft constraints	D5.2
	Terrain layers	D5.1
	Wind energy scenarios	D5.2
Transmission lines	D5.2	
User account	Sign up and login	D5.2

	Edit personal info page	D5.2
	Overview of saved simulations with share option	D5.2

Help

To explain each dataset and model in an understandable way, a dataset description was created for each layer on the map and result of the wind farm simulation (side panel). The dataset descriptions can be accessed by clicking on the new-tab icon next to the info button (Figure 6). These descriptions are publicly available in the general forum.

Figure 6: Link to dataset description in the forum is available for each layer and result in the wind farm simulation.

Wind farm simulation

In the final version, it is possible to choose, when running a wind farm simulation, whether the tool takes into account both **hard and soft**

constraints, or hard constraints only. The user can select this in the “Select parameters” pop-up after creating a region of interest for a wind farm simulation (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Pop-up to select parameters for a new wind farm simulation.

Additionally, more results have been added to the side panel of the wind farm simulation. On the top of the side panel the turbine details are added to show the specifications of the simulated wind turbines. Here the hub height, rotor diameter and rated power or specified together with the parameters selected for the simulation (Figure 8).

The **regulations warning** (Figure 8) was updated to reflect the median setback distances that were assembled in the WIMBY project for the investigated European countries. Finally, also the local setback distances are updated. The final version shows the regulations that apply in the user’s region of interest with the latest results from the WIMBY project (March 2025). More information about the regulations can be found in deliverable D2.10 (Bucha et al., 2024).

Figure 8: Wind farm simulation results for an example in Belgium. In the side panel the turbine details are shown and the general tab is open with the regulation warning.

On the top of the side panel a discard and save button are now available to respectively discard or save a simulation (Figure 9). Saving a simulation is only possible when a user is logged in (more information in the User account section).

Figure 9: Top part of the side panel with the discard and save simulation buttons. In the info text it is explained that you need to log in before it is possible to save.

The impact tab also received some updates (Figure 10). The visualisation of the **noise impact** was improved as well as the model. More information about the noise model can be found in deliverable D2.3 (Sacchi et al., 2023). The **shadow flicker impact** can also be added on the map to visualise the estimated impacted locations (Figure 10). The new model also takes into consideration the topography of the location and the presentation of the results has been simplified considerably. Two colours identify locations with less than 30h of shadow flicker per year and more than 30h (a threshold mentioned in many regulations in European countries). More information

about the shadow flicker can be found in deliverable D2.3 (Sacchi et al., 2023).

Figure 10: Impact tab of wind farm simulation with the noise and shadow flicker impact visible on the map.

Another impact displayed in the side panel is the **land use and land cover change** (LULC). When the component is folded in the side panel it only shows a summary value to indicate the percentage of LULC in the simulated wind farm. When the component is unfolded the extent of the wind farm is shown on the map and a small table is visible (Figure 11). In this table the land use types with changes in the wind farm extent are listed together with the area and % of change. More information about the LULC can be found in deliverable D1.4 (Mikovits, 2024).

Figure 11: Impact tab of wind farm simulation results with the wind farm area delineated that was used to calculate the land use change shown on the map.

Next in the list of impacts is the estimation of the **Levelised Cost of Electricity (LCOE)**, shown in euro per kWh (Figure 12). To calculate this cost, the model computes the grid connection to the nearest substation. Users can also visualize the path of the cable on the map. More information about the LCOE can be found in deliverable D2.2 (Hahmann et al., 2024a).

Figure 12: Levelised Cost of Electricity impact with grid connection visible on the map.

One of the positive impacts is the estimation of **created jobs** (Figure 13). Folded the total amount of job-years is shown that will be created by the simulated wind farm. To see the share of this total number of job-years per lifetime, the user has to unfold the component. It is also possible to see the

difference between direct, indirect and induced jobs. More information about the job creation model can be found in deliverable D2.10 (Bucha et al., 2024).

Figure 13: The estimated job-years created by a simulated wind farm, shown as the share per life stage and type (direct, indirect or induced).

The next impact shown in the side panel is the **collision risk for birds and bats** (Figure 14). The vulnerability or number of species potentially at risk is available for birds. The mortality or number of individuals expected to fatally collide with wind turbines can also be viewed. More information about the collision risk impact can be found in deliverable D1.6 (Etard et al., 2024).

Figure 14: The collision risk is available with the vulnerability for birds and the mortality for birds and bats.

The **landscape scenicness** is also displayed as an impact (Figure 15). This impact is only shown (as a kind of warning) if the scenicness value is “highly scenic”. More information about the landscape scenicness can be found in deliverable D2.5 (R. Chen et al., 2023).

Figure 15: Indication of scenicness in the wind farm simulation impacts.

Another positive impact available in the side panel is the **local benefits** (Figure 16). This impact shows the type of local benefit for the region of your interest (region drawn on the map). If information is available for multiple levels or there is an overlap in regions, e.g. the country and regional level, they are all available and can be selected in the dropdown. The component can be folded open to see the full description of the benefits. If available, links are also shown to examples or legislative websites. More information about the local benefits can be found in deliverable D2.10 (Bucha et al., 2024).

Figure 16: The local benefits are positive impacts for local residents or communities formulated at the regional or country level.

The **environmental impact over the turbine(s) life** is the final impact calculated for a wind farm simulation. It shows the g of CO₂eq per produced kWh of energy by the wind farm (Figure 17). The model was updated since the first version of the map as described in deliverable D5.1. More information about how the environmental impact was calculated, can be found in deliverable D2.8 (Huber & Lavigne Philippot, 2024).

Environmental impact over the turbine(s) life

46 gCO₂eq/kWh

Figure 17: The environmental impact of the turbine(s) life expressed in g CO₂eq/kWh is calculated with a Life Cycle Assessment.

Pilot regions

One of the layers users can activate on the map is the overview of the pilot regions. The information displayed in the side panel was updated in comparison to the first version in deliverable D5.1. For Styria, Pantelleria and Rogaland (Karmøy) the results of the **impact assessment on marine and land fauna** is now available. More information about the datasets can be found in deliverable D1.8 (Diengdoh et al., 2025).

For **Styria** the habitat suitability of amphibians, bats, birds and butterflies is displayed for specific species and the whole group. For bats only one species was investigated. Users can take a look which locations in the regions are the most suitable for certain animal species (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Updated pilot site information with the results of the habitat suitability analysis for Styria (for the amphibian group).

For **Pantelleria** the habitat suitability is available for a number of dolphins, fish, rays, reptile and shark species. Users can activate the species and see which parts of the sea around the island is suitable for a certain species (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Updated pilot site information with the results of the habitat suitability analysis for Pantelleria (for dolphin species „Tursiops-truncatus“).

For **Rogaland** the wind farm sensitivity index (WSI) can be consulted on the map for a number of different seabird species (Figure 20). The sensitivity data is available on the scale of the whole coast around Norway and for different seasons.

Figure 20: Updated pilot site information with the results of the Windfarm sensitivity analysis for Rogaland, Norway (for the species „Uria-lomvia“).

About

On the top right, in the menu, users can find the link to the Terms of use, that specify the terms and conditions that apply when using the interactive map.

In [this document](#) the terms of use, privacy policy and disclaimer are described (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Menu with the link to the terms of use, General forum and project website.

Users can contact the WIMBY team through the WIMBY forum if they have questions about the application, the datasets, the models, etc... (Figure 22) In the forum also a help guide is available to help users of the WIMBY map get started. This welcome kit explains the functionalities of the tools.

Figure 22: Welcome kit on the WIMBY forum with instructions on how to use the forum, map and the dataset descriptions.

Languages

The interactive map is available in all the languages of the pilot sites of the WIMBY project. On the top right it is possible to switch from English to one of the other languages by selecting the correct abbreviation (Figure 23).

- EN = English
- DE= German
- PT = Portuguese
- NN=Nynorsk (Norwegian)

- NB= Bokmål (Norwegian)
- IT= Italian

For Norwegian, two languages were made available that are relevant for the pilot site in Rogaland. The translations were created with help from the consortium partners.

Figure 23: Component on the top right with the language selector based on abbreviations.

Existing wind turbines

In the final version another new dataset available in the layer component is the **existing wind turbines** layer (Figure 24). Users need to zoom in on the map to see the locations of the individual wind turbines. On hover, users can consult the type of turbine, the hub height, rated power and the rotor diameter for each turbine in the dataset. More information about the existing wind turbines data can be found in Deliverable D2.2 (Hahmann et al., 2024a).

Figure 24: Existing wind turbines dataset with extra information: turbine type, hub height, rated power and rotor diameter.

Forum functionalities

In the menu on the top right, users can find a link to navigate to the WIMBY General forum (Figure 21). The authentication of both tools was integrated to make sure that users interested in both the map and the forum only have

to create one account (Figure 25). Users that create an account on the WIMBY map can also login to the WIMBY forum and vice versa.

Figure 25: Shared login feature on the WIMBY forum to sign up for a shared account or login with the WIMBY map account on the forum.

Map layers

Multiple map layers were added in comparison to the first version of the WIMBY map (as described in Deliverable D5.1). The approach with the layer panel on the top left is still the same but more categories were added as well as a link to the descriptive dataset for each layer (Figure 26). By default, the mean wind speed is activated when the interactive map is opened. Below an overview is displayed of all the layers and the new and updated datasets are explained further.

Figure 26: Map layer component in the final version of the WIMBY interactive map.

The following layers are available per category:

- Wind resource
 - Mean wind speed (100m, 200m)
 - Power density (100m, 200m)
- Impacts
 - Collision risk
 - Human health impacts
 - Landscape scenicness
- Energy
 - Wind power scenarios
 - Transmission lines
- Terrain
 - Elevation
 - Ruggedness index
- Exclusion zones
 - Hard constraints

- Soft constraints
 - Existing wind turbines
 - Pilot sites

The first layer available in the impacts category is the **collision risk for birds and bats** (Figure 27). The user can select the mortality layer for bats and the vulnerability layer for birds. More information about these datasets can be found in deliverable D1.6 (Etard et al., 2024).

Figure 27: The collision risk impact layer for bats shown as the bats mortality values for the European continent.

The second dataset in this category is the **human health impacts** layer, which shows an estimation of cumulative health effects of wind farm accidents (Figure 28). For each NUTS2 region the Disability-Adjusted Life Years per Gigawatt-Electric year are shown with categories. More information about this map layer can be found in deliverable D2.3 (Sacchi et al., 2023).

Figure 28: The human health impacts layer shown as categories from very low to very high for each NUTS2 region.

The third layer available in the impacts is the **landscape scenicness** (Figure 29). This dataset is only consultable for Great Britain as a result of thorough validation thanks to the ScenicOrNot project. This layer indicates locations in Great Britain that were found to be highly scenic in comparison to other locations with less of a scenic value. More information about this map layer can be found in deliverable D2.5 (R. Chen et al., 2024).

Figure 29: Landscape scenicness map layer for Great Britain.

In the energy category the first layer shows the **modelled wind capacity in 2050** depending on environmental and social constraints (Figure 30). Users can switch both constraints from low, medium to high and see how this

affects the distribution of the wind capacity in the NUTS2 regions in Europe. The installed capacity is shown in GW with circles on the map. The size of the circles is related to the size of the value for each region. The dataset is available for onshore and offshore wind power. More information about this dataset can be found in deliverable D4.5 (Price et al., 2025).

Figure 30: Estimated installed capacity (in GW) for each NUTS2 region in Europe depending on the level environmental and social impacts are taken into account.

Additionally, the **transmission line** network based on OpenStreetMap data (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2025) can be visualised as a layer after zooming in on the map (Figure 31). This is another factor that has to be taken into account in wind farm planning.

Figure 31: Transmission lines layer that shows the transmission network after zooming in.

In the exclusion zones category the first layer is the hard constraints, showing the locations where you cannot build a wind farm due to constraints such as e.g., nature reserves, built-up area, roads, and water bodies (Figure 32). The soft constraints layer also takes into account buffers and additional categories with median distance offsets derived from regulations in European countries. These layers are also only available after zooming in far enough on the map. More information about these datasets can be found in deliverable D2.2 (Hahmann et al. 2024a).

Figure 32: Hard constraints layer showing exclusion zones in 4 different categories: ecology, land use, infrastructure and physical limitations.

User account

In the final version of the WIMBY map, a number of functionalities were introduced linked to authentication. By default, a user is not logged in when opening map.wimby.eu and the user menu can be opened by clicking on the user icon on the top right (Figure 33). Users can click on “Login” to navigate to the login screen where new users can also create an account. To create an account, minimal personal information needs to be shared: only a valid email address, username and password (Figure 34). Users can open the terms of use and privacy policy before they create an account.

Figure 33: Login button to sign in for existing users or create an account for new users.

Sign up
Create a new account.

Email address

Preferred username

Password

Confirm password

Show password

By signing up, you agree to our [Terms of Use](#) and [Privacy Policy](#)

Sign up

Have an account already? [Sign in](#)

Figure 34: Creating an account on the WIMBY map only requires an email address, username and password. Links to the terms of use and privacy policy are also provided.

When a user is logged in, the username is shown on the top right and multiple options are available in the user menu (Figure 35). Users can change their username or email address and reset their password in the “Personal info” page.

Figure 35: User menu with multiple options after login: logout, the links to the personal info and my simulation pages.

The “my simulations” page shows an overview of the saved simulations and gives the user the ability to open them, share the link, edit the name or delete them (Figure 36).

Figure 36: An overview of the saved simulations is shown on a dedicated page with the possibility to open, share, edit and delete saved simulations.

3.1.2 WIMBY general forum

The purpose of the WIMBY General Forum is to allow all members interested in wind-power planning to discuss in a focused digital environment. Users of the WIMBY interactive map have the possibility to share their simulations and create related discussion threads. Through the Forum each member

can highlight problems and/or propose solutions related to potential issues arising with existing, planned, or proposed wind-power deployments. Also, discussions can focus on further aspects and impacts not directly related to wind-power which could feed the informed opinion building of involved stakeholders and communities. As an example, members would share a link to their simulation in the appropriate category “Public simulations” (see Figure 37).

Public simulations

Share here the link to your simulation. To start a simulation sign-up and start using the WIMBY Interactive Map at www.map.wimby.eu. You will find your simulations in the personal area. Copy-paste the link and your comment in a new topic under this category to receive other members' feedback.

Public simulations tags Latest New Hot Top New Topic

Topic	Replies	Views	Activity
<p>🚩 About the Public simulations category</p> <p>Share here the link to your simulation. To start a simulation sign-up and start using the WIMBY Interactive Map at www.map.wimby.eu. You will find your simulations in the personal area. Copy-paste the link and your comment in a new topic under this category to receive other members' feedback. read more</p>	0	1	Sep 29
A test simulation of a wind farm in France, Trooz	1	9	3d
Test simulation: Wind park in Burgenland, Austria	1	7	14d
Multiplying the installed capacity of Slovenia x2	0	5	14d
My first simulation of a wind farm in Stuttgart	0	3	14d

Figure 37: Category in the WIMBY General Forum for discussing shared wind farm simulations.

To this aim, members would create a dedicated thread to share opinions or ask questions to the WIMBY researchers. Other members would then be able to see, read and reply to the thread, adding screenshots, media files and links to motivate their replies (see Figure 38 below).

Test simulation: Wind park in Burgenland, Austria

Public simulations

EvaSchoell 14d

map.wimby.eu

WIMBY 2

Wind In My Backyard - Nickelsdorf, Burgenland

1 ❤️ 🗨️ 📌 ↩️ Reply

8 1 views link

Nov 14

1/2

Nov 14

rebecca_user 14d

Be careful of setback distances:

14d ago

Figure 38: Example of shared wind farm simulation in the forum.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable (D5.2) explains the methodology and final results for the WIMBY platform (WIMBY map and forum) developed within WP5 of the WIMBY project. Both the WIMBY map and forum are now publicly available at map.wimby.eu and forum.wimby.eu.

Building further on the conceptualisation efforts from the first part of the project it was possible to create user-friendly tools focusing on the needs of the end users. In the second phase of the project, the focus was set on integrating all the spatial datasets and models developed in the WIMBY project into the interactive map. In a final workshop the visualisation of these different results was co-created together with the consortium partners. The further development of the tools was made possible through a strong cooperation between WP5 partners. An integrated authentication was established to enable users to use the same account for logging into both tools. In conclusion the project results are showcased in the WIMBY platform and enable stakeholders to receive the right information for decision making.

In a next step, we are looking for ways to keep improving the tools developed in the WIMBY project. In the development the efforts were focused on successful implementation of the must have requirements. In the co-creation process we identified a multitude of potential further developments that would be useful for the target audiences but are beyond the scope of the resources available in the WIMBY project. For now, and fortunately, the Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development of Utrecht University has provided a contract to NAZKA to work further on the WIMBY map game that was ideated and described in deliverable D5.1. Finally, we are also looking for a way to strengthen the information in the tool for offshore wind planning and, in general, for institutional and commercial support to keep the tool running and open access in the long-term.

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ANNEX

4.1 Exclusion zones data sources

Table 3: Exclusion zones and their hard and soft constraints as buffers in meters. The processing of every subcategory

Dataset	Category	Sub-category	Hard buffer	Soft buffer
Copernicus DEM - Global and European Digital Elevation Model (2022)	Slope	slope	<15 deg	<15 deg
CORINE Land Cover 2018 (vector), Europe, 6-yearly. (2019)	Buildings and urban areas	residential areas	0m	725m
World Settlement Footprint (2019)		residential buildings	0m	725m
OpenStreetMap (2025)	Onshore infrastructure	airports	800m	2000m
		military	75m	1000m
		radar	2000m	6000m [and 44500m, if in a military area]
		transmission lines	21m	218m
		railways	3m	187m
		roads highways	3m	187m

			roads primary	3m	105m
EMODnet Activities, Telecommunication, Actual Routes (2023)	Human Cables, Offshore infrastructure		gas pipelines	0.61m	222m
			offshore cables	0.1m	0m
EU-Hydro Network Database 2006-2012, Europe - version 1.3. (2020)	River Database Europe - version 1.3. (2020)	Hydrology	waters rivers	0m	50m
			waters standing	0m	50m
Nationally designated areas for public access (2023)	Protected areas		nature conservation	0m	200m
UK CDDA 2020v01 (2020)					
EMODnet Activities Density Map (2023)	Human Vessel	Shipping lanes	shipping lanes	0m	500m

4.2 Results data visualisation workshop

Figure 39: Results data visualisation workshop for the regulations and local benefits datasets.

Figure 40: Results of the data visualisation workshop for the landscape scenicness dataset.

Figure 41: Results of the data visualisation workshop for the Land Use Change dataset.

Figure 42: Results of the data visualisation workshop for the shadow flicker dataset.

Figure 43: Results of the data visualisation workshop for the wind resource dataset.

